

Full length article

The Exploding Wire: A novel ignition source for the determination of safety characteristics of dusts and hybrid mixtures[☆]

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ABSTRACT

For the determination of safety characteristics of dusts there are mainly chemical igniters in use. Especially for the maximum explosion pressure and the maximum rate of pressure rise there is no standard with another ignition source. The chemical igniters have the disadvantage of being very hard to obtain in most countries and they are even illegal in some. This leads to the fact, that those countries are not able to investigate the safety characteristics or only with a high effort by sending dust samples to facilities outside the country. This article presents a novel ignition source and describes how to build it. It is also the first step to place this ignition source into the dust standards in the future.

1. Introduction

1.1. State of the art and the need for an alternative ignition source

The ignition source and energy affect the determined values of the safety characteristics [1,2]. One problem of the standardized ignition sources that are commonly used for gas explosions is that they are too weak to ignite dusts under turbulence and with that might lead to unsafe safety characteristics. Another problem is that their energy supply is normally coupled with the power grid having 50 Hz. This causes additional ignition delay times between 0 and 20 ms (see Fig. 1) which leads to flawed values due to a possible settlement of turbulence and dust (see Fig. 2).

The chemical igniters on the other hand, the only standardized ignition source for the determination of the maximum explosion pressure and maximum rate of pressure rise of dusts, have an unspecified burning duration and might cause overdriving of gaseous mixtures, leading to highly conservative safety characteristics and with that to overpriced safety measures. The tests in the 20L-sphere, once adapted from the standard 1 m³-vessel are known to show discrepancies since especially the two 5 kJ igniters fill the whole sphere with sparks which

is not the case for the 1 m³-vessel [3–6]. Since the timing, the overall burning duration and with that the energy density cannot be controlled with the chemical igniters, the investigation of the comparability of the safety characteristics for these two vessel sizes might be increased with a precisely controllable ignition source. The need for an alternative ignition source is also visible if the dust testing laboratories in the world are marked. The countries which are allowed to import chemical igniters, that are necessary for the determination of the maximum explosion pressure and the maximum rate of pressure rise, are marked in red (see Fig. 3).

Brazil is marked reddish, since there is only one facility that is allowed to import the igniters and they have to be delivered by the military. Chinese dust testing laboratories manufacture their own igniters since the restrictions are very high. In Russia there are dust testing laboratories but the standard igniters are not allowed to be delivered anymore. In India there is no single facility for the determination of p_{max} and $(dp/dt)_{max}$ of dusts since the igniters are prohibited, so the companies have to either ship the dust samples to the United Kingdom or forego the tests. The same applies for Southern America except for that one facility. In Africa there is also just one dust testing

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Nomenclature

(dp/dt)	Rate of pressure rise
$(dp/dt)_{max}$	Maximum rate of pressure rise
K_{St}	Volume-normalized deflagration index for dusts
K_G	Volume-normalized deflagration index for gases
p_{max}	Maximum explosion pressure
LEL	Lower explosion limit
MEC	Minimum explosible concentration
X-Wire	Exploding Wire

Fig. 1. Additional delay for the standard exploding wire device.
Source: Taken from [7]

Fig. 2. Decay of the turbulent kinetic energy in a 20L-sphere, calculated from the measured root mean square velocity.

Source: Taken from [8]

facility in South Africa, making it almost impossible to implement safety measures.

Other laboratories are also investigating the influence of the ignition sources and developing new ones for the determination of safety characteristics.

There are currently at least four different approaches to a new ignition source:

- The technical University of Bratislava is working on alternative chemical [9] and various other types of ignition sources [10]
- The University of Pardubice together with OZM Research is investigating squibs for the activation of airbags as alternative ignition source for the determination of safety characteristics of dusts [6,11]

Fig. 3. Worldmap with the countries, that perform dust explosion tests (CC BY-SA 3.0 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/User:Cbrittain10>, image cut and marked by the corr. author, taken from [7]).

- The University of Orleans is working with an adjustable permanent spark ignition source [12–14]
- The University of Lorraine in Nancy and INERIS are developing a new ignition device with an adjustable permanent spark [15]

For hybrid mixtures and for precise results, the requirements are even stricter so a new ignition source was developed and tested in this thesis.

1.2. Exploding wires

Exploding wires (X-Wires) consist of a thin (usually under 0.5 mm) metal wires and a power source, usually a capacitor. If the current is passed through the wire it heats up due to ohmic heating, melts, then evaporates generating a lower resistance path allowing even higher currents to pass through. Due to more heating it finally expands and ends the whole process [16].

X-wires¹ have been investigated for a long period of time.

The first (rather disturbing) publication found is from Edward Nairne in 1774 who connected long (several feet) wires of iron, silver and platinum wires to a series of leyden jars (preliminary form of capacitors). Further he connected a duck, a turkey and a rooster between the electrodes. All three animals died in these experiments [17].

Faraday used X-wires of thin gold to deposit layers of very thin gold on glass and other materials [18].

With the beginning of the 20th century the research on X-wires accelerated and with the development of new measurement and highspeed-camera techniques the insights on the exploding mechanism became clearer (for a historic overview see [19]).

Their first well-recognized technical application was the ignition of the Fat-Man atomic bomb in 1944 because the precise timing was needed for the initiation of multiple explosives to compress the plutonium [20].

Today X-wires are used broadly in scientific research and in technology and engineering: Rososhek et al. investigated the shock waves of different metals exploding under water using schlieren-imaging [21]. Virozub et al. investigated the influence of the skin effect of X-wires and arrays of X-wires having equal cross sections than the single wire under water [22]. Mellor et al. used X-wire devices to study the interaction between multiple shock waves [23]. In a review article Oreshkin and Baksht investigate X-wires in vacuum to obtain a better understanding of the fundamentals of the explosion mechanism [24]. Adamanian and Shneerson investigated the plasma acceleration of X-wires in strong magnetic fields [25].

¹ Sometimes confusingly referred to as “fuse wires” or “melting wires” in the literature. Because of the high energy discharge causing the wire to explode and not only to melt or to break we only refer here to it as exploding wire or rather X-Wire.

Fig. 4. Fully assembled exploding wire device, turned on but uncharged.

Fig. 5. Opened device with all components inside.

Fig. 6. Circuit of one channel for the exploding wire device, C1 = capacitors, L1 = inductance, T1 = thyristor, W1 = wire, E1 and E2 = electrodes.
Source: Taken from [7]

While the former ones were more fundamental research others focused on applications: The technique can be used for the production of nano-powders of the wire-material [26–28]. A high-voltage detonator was used for the ignition of the Titan IV space rocket fuel [29].

Another application is the use of an X-wire as light source for special applications. The special features - high light intensity [30], higher reproducibility compared to chemical flash fires ($\pm 5\%$ fluctuation of the emission was already possible in 1951 for X-wires) and adjustment of color with different materials [31] - make this technique invaluable for some applications. A main usecase is still the initiation of safe explosives [32].

1.3. X-wires in explosion protection

X-wires were used before in explosion protection for a variety of materials being gaseous, liquid or solid. Takahashi et al. [33] used different types of metals and diameters to investigate the explosion limits of methane mixed with air. Scheid et al. [34] compared the safety characteristics determined with a single-channel X-wire device with those determined with single chemical igniters for lignite, corn starch, niacin, anthraquinone and steel dust. The results were comparable, when the same ignition energies were used for all five dusts.

They also investigated the flame propagation and behavior of the different types and compared them amongst each other [35,36].

Krietsch et al. [37] compared a double channel X-wire device to chemical igniters looking at the flame propagation as well as the determined safety characteristics. The tested dusts, lignite, corn starch, niacin and anthraquinone, showed comparable safety characteristics when determined with 2×1 kJ and 2×5 kJ X-wires and chemical igniters.

Spitzer et al. determined the delivered ignition energy of an adjustable X-wire device (similar to the one that is described here) with a bomb calorimeter and compared it to the electrically measured energy. The burning duration and the angle of the electrodes was also investigated [38]. The CAD and the PCB (printed circuit board) for the calorimeter used in their work are available on request and the calorimeter has been successfully rebuilt and used in eight research facilities across Europe.

In another article they determined the volume of the light arc for two different X-wire devices using schlieren-imaging [5].

2. Materials and methods

The device consists of the following main parts:

- Five capacitors per channel with 4700 μ F each
- One thyristor per channel
- One inductance per channel
- Two electrodes per channel
- One transformer to deliver the 450 V with two secondary windings
- Enclosure
- Two electrodes per channel
- Lid for the 20L-sphere
- Additional parts for the wiring

A full assembled device can be seen in Fig. 4, the inside in Fig. 5, the circuit of one channel is displayed in Fig. 6.

The general setup, how to connect all the devices is displayed in Fig. 7: The four electrodes (only two displayed in the figure) are connected to the X-Wire device. The output of the controller that normally triggers the chemical igniters is connected to the BNC connector at the front of the device. The PC is connected to the controller. The blue button is pushed for loading and the two voltmeters show the voltage that is stored in the capacitors. The voltmeters are analogue and work also, if the device is unplugged as an additional safety measure. The loading button is also breaking the circuit for the BNC connector so that the device can never be triggered while being load. The red button is pushed before starting the test procedure. If not pushed the signal coming into the BNC connector does not trigger the device, assuring another safety level.

Fig. 7. Schematic of the setup for the dust explosion tests.

Fig. 9. Schematic of the high voltage source.

Fig. 8. CAD of the mounting for the thyristors.

Fig. 10. CAD of the mounting for the capacitors.

Fig. 11. Schematic of the capacitors.

The mounting for the two thyristors was 3D-printed and is displayed in Fig. 8.

The loading circuit consists of a transformer with two secondary windings having a rated secondary voltage of 340 V (peak voltage of $340 \text{ V} * \sqrt{2} = 480 \text{ V}$). The secondary voltage is rectified using four 1N4007-diodes. On the primary side a solid-state relay is used to switch the loading on and off (see Fig. 9).

Five capacitors per channel were assembled in parallel. The mounting was also 3D-printed and is displayed in Fig. 10.

As a safety measure a resistance was also placed in parallel. In any case of false loading or insufficient deloading during the ignition this resistance ensures deloading the fully loaded (450 V) capacitors in 37 min to 60 V which is the critical value for DC [39], see R5 in Fig. 11. Moving iron anemometers were chosen for displaying the voltage because they do not need an extra power source and with that work even if the device is unplugged.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Discharge and energy quantification

Before the new reduced device was built several studies were conducted with a similar double-channel device with an adjustable and online measurable ignition energy.

To ensure a similar ignition energy to that of the chemical igniters, the energy that is actually introduced into the system was measured. This is lower than the energy that is stored in the capacitors before the discharge due to losses in the circuit (especially in the inductance) and some residual energy that is still stored after the discharge.

The energy was measured in two ways: With a calorimeter and by measuring the current and voltage during the discharge. The ignition devices for the X-wire had built-in isolation amplifiers, which provided the voltage (Fig. 12) and current (Fig. 13) during the ignition process galvanically isolated with a defined factor as measuring voltage. The galvanic isolation and the factors were necessary to prevent voltages of 450 V from being applied to the front panel, which would pose a significant hazard to the user.

Fig. 12. Voltage curve at 450 V ignition voltage and 1070 J ignition energy.

Fig. 13. Ignition current curve at 450 V ignition voltage and 1070 J ignition energy.

Fig. 14. Power curve at 450 V ignition voltage and 1070 J ignition energy; product of ignition voltage and ignition current.

Fig. 15. Summed power at 450 V ignition voltage and 1070 J ignition energy.

Fig. 16. Comparison of two 1 kJ chemical igniters and two 1 kJ exploding wires, 1 ms, 2 ms and 5 ms after the first visible sign of explosion.

The product of the measured ignition voltage and the measured ignition current gives the power in the moment (Fig. 14), the sum the overall energy (Fig. 15):

$$P_{\text{ignition}} = U * I \tag{1}$$

$$E_{\text{ignition}} = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{U_k * I_k}{n} \right) \tag{2}$$

The voltage is measured with a voltage divider, the ignition current by means of a shunt resistor with a resistance of 0.5 mΩ. The voltage drop due to the resistance of the cable is subtracted from the measured voltage according to the following equation:

$$U_{\text{res}} = U_{\text{meas.}} - \frac{\rho_{\text{copper}} * l_{\text{cable}} * I_{\text{meas.}}}{A_{\text{cable}}} \tag{3}$$

3.2. Igniting volume and duration

If the thyristor is triggered by an injecting current, the thin wires between the electrodes evaporate thus forming two electric arcs, the actual ignition source (see Fig. 16).

The duration of the two different igniters is hard to compare because the X-wires donate all their energy into the system in 10 ms and even with schlieren-imaging only smoke is visible after 50 ms while the

Fig. 17. Highspeed footage of one 1 kJ chemical igniter.

Fig. 18. Highspeed Schlieren footage of one 1 kJ X-wire.

Fig. 19. Measured explosion pressures for hexane with reference data [40,41].

chemical igniters are still showing signs of sparks up to 350 ms after activation. However, the “main” time seems comparable (Figs. 17 and 18).

3.3. Comparison of safety characteristics

Most of the results were published in the references cited in Section 1.2, those that have not been published before are described here in brief.

The safety characteristics of the single components and their hybrid mixture were determined for a risk assessment of the extraction process of soy oil from soy flour using hexane as solvent. X-wires with two times 1 kJ and chemical igniters having the same ignition energy were used and their safety characteristics compared for hexane (see Fig. 19). Literature values for the LEL, UEL and p_{max} are also inserted for comparability. It shall be pointed out, that all values are not corrected like in the dust standards. All tests at the highest values as well as the ones at the limits were repeated at least twice to an overall number of three tests.

There are no literature values for the rate of pressure rise of hexane,² the results obtained in this work are displayed in Fig. 20.

² Due to the turbulence, that is inherent when testing dusts, the obtained values shall not be used for direct comparison with hexane under quiescent conditions.

Fig. 20. Measured rates of pressure rise for hexane.

The results for hexane show three things: The results for the explosion pressure are comparable but the results for the lower and upper explosion limits seem to be better with the X-wires since they are not exceeding the common threshold value of 0.5 bar outside the explosion region. Also, the results for the rate of pressure rise are also comparable but on average slightly higher than those obtained with the chemical igniters. This may be caused by a preciser and earlier triggering of the ignition source. The chemical igniters showed an additional delay due to the chemical explosion after the ignition is electrically triggered [7] while the X-wires do not show that behavior and with that lead to an explosion at an earlier moment with a higher level of turbulence.

A list of dusts, which were compared using 2 kJ and 10 kJ for both, chemical igniters and X-wires, is shown in Table 1. All tests were performed three times according to the dust standards. For most dusts the reduction of the ignition energy to 2 kJ instead of 10 kJ and an exchange to X-wires did not affect the determined safety characteristics. It is not clear yet what causes the discrepancy of the nano dusts, especially because the tested ones (aluminum) are conductive. So it might either be the dust acting as a conductor for the light arc or the special behavior of the nano dust itself. However, for organic dusts the X-wire seems like a suitable device. Values for hybrid mixtures that were determined with X-wires and chemical igniters of the same ignition energy are displayed in Table 2.

4. Conclusions

A new type of ignition source was developed for the determination of safety characteristics of dusts and hybrid mixtures. The results obtained with it are comparable to those determined with chemical igniters.

The new device has the benefits, that once built it can be used numerous times. Also it does not fall under any restrictions concerning state laws because no explosives are used for this ignition device. It has limitations when the dusts, that shall be tested, are conductive such as metals or some carbon dusts.

It is planned to develop a criterion for the applicability of this device where the conductivity of the dust serves as an indicator whether this device can replace the chemical igniters or not.

Another benefit is the precise timing which is one requirement for comparable results of the safety characteristics due to the decaying turbulence inside the test vessels. The adjustment of the ignition energy and its online measurement may be implemented as well for scientific reasons, two more benefits that are harder to achieve (adjustment)

Table 1

List of dusts which were compared using exploding wires (X-W) and chemical igniters; marked red, if the discrepancy exceeded the common value of $\pm 10\%$ for p_{max} or $\pm 20\%$ for K_{St} ; all values were processed with the usual equations given in the dust standards.

Dust		2 × 1 kJ		2 × 5 kJ	
		X-W	Chem.	X-W	Chem.
Corn starch Median: 14 μm	p_{max}	8.1	8.3	8.2	8.4
	K_{St}	150	146	154	153
Niacin Median: 15 μm	p_{max}	8.7	8.9	8.6	8.3
	K_{St}	287	272	302	264
Anthraquinone Median: 12 μm	p_{max}	8	8.1	8.1	8.6
	K_{St}	314	261	308	309
Dye powder #2 Median: 8 μm	p_{max}	7.9	–	8.1	8.2
	K_{St}	198	–	182	194
Dye powder #3 Median: 8 μm	p_{max}	8.9	–	9.1	9.1
	K_{St}	283	–	286	271
Milk powder Median: 37 μm	p_{max}	7.8	7.3	–	7.0
	K_{St}	111	94	–	107
Wood dust Median: 37 μm	p_{max}	7.4	–	–	7.9
	K_{St}	97	–	–	107
Wood dust Median: 32 μm	p_{max}	6.8	–	–	7.0
	K_{St}	69	–	–	74
Avobenzon Median: 24 μm	p_{max}	6.8	–	–	6.7
	K_{St}	180	–	–	163
Lignite Median: 35 μm	p_{max}	7.5	7.2	8.2	8.4
	K_{St}	192	170	214	218
Aluminum Median: 2 μm	p_{max}	9.5	9.6	10.2	10.4
	K_{St}	588	636	944	788
Aluminum nano Median: 18 nm	p_{max}	6.8	–	–	7.1
	K_{St}	138	–	–	164
Aluminum nano 40–60 nm	p_{max}	7.6	–	–	8.9
	K_{St}	361	–	–	621
Aluminum nano 50–70 nm	p_{max}	7.7	–	–	8.3
	K_{St}	213	–	–	427
Aluminum nano 90–110 nm	p_{max}	7.6	–	–	7.9
	K_{St}	162	–	–	299

Table 2

Values for hybrid mixture consisting of corn starch and methane.

Dust+Gas		2 × 1 kJ	
		X-W	Chem.
Corn starch +3% Methane	p_{max}	8.4	8.5
	K_{St}	214	193
Corn starch +6% Methane	p_{max}	7.9	7.8
	K_{St}	331	271
Corn starch +9% Methane	p_{max}	7.9	7.9
	K_{St}	486	421

or rather impossible (online measurement) with the chemical igniters. However, this device is mainly focused on a stable ignition energy and for the application for companies dealing with dusts.

Supplementary materials

DISCLAIMER: NEITHER THE AUTHORS NOR THEIR AFFILIATIONS TAKE RESPONSIBILITY FOR ANY DAMAGE TO EQUIPMENT OR HARM TO PERSONAL CAUSED BY THE REPLICATION OF THIS DEVICE.

The files for the PCB for the galvanically isolated trigger control can be found under the url <https://aisler.net/p/YJXNWZKQ>, a possible power supply under the url <https://aisler.net/p/VMVPSICC>.

The CAD-files for the mountings for the capacitors, the thyristors and the lid with four electrodes will be send on request.

The following list provides suitable parts for the building of the device. If the parts are commonly used and not rare they are not specified further. If the parts are very special a potential supplier and the URL is stated.

- 8 Diodes 1N4007
- 1 Transformer with two 340 V secondary voltages. <https://www.buerklin.com/de/Netztransformator-Netz--110%C2%A0V-240%C2%A0V/p/12C160>
- 10 capacitors with 4700 μF and 450 V <https://de.rs-online.com/web/p/aluminium-elektrolytkondensatoren/1251084>
- 2 Inductances with 5.6 mH and 0.05 Ohm https://www.mundorf.com/audio/de/shop/coils/ei_coils/MCoil-FERON-Null-Ohm/?card=6130
- 2 Thyristors <https://www.tme.eu/de/details/t100n12-gg/thyristoren-mit-schraubverb/greengoo/t100n12/or> <https://www.semic-shop.de/skt-100-18e-15/>
- 2 Resistors with 47 kΩ and 11 W
- 2 Resistors with 33 Ωm and 25 W
- 1 Solid-state relay with 250 V, 10 A and 3–24 V control voltage
- 2 Moving iron ammeters to show the loading voltage
- Triggercontrol printed circuit board <https://aisler.net/p/VMVPSICC>
- 9 Volt power supply circuit board <https://aisler.net/p/YJXNWZKQ>
- 230 V Switch with lamp
- BNC-connector - Trigger
- Button with blue light - loading
- Button with red light - Ready

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Stefan H. Spitzer: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fabian Reitmeier:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Enrico Danzi:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Bretislav Janovsky:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Michael Paul:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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